

PROCEEDINGS OF THE MEETING OF THE BOARD OF STUDIES OF THE COLLEGE OF MANAGEMENT & COMMERCE, SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY HELD On 14.07.2022 AT 3.30 P.M. IN THE CONFERENCE ROOM, 2ND FLOOR, PANDESHWARA CAMPUS, SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY.

Members Present:

Prof Keerthan Raj	Chairperson
Prof. Amith Menezes	Member
Prof. Nelson Periera	Member
Dr. Shailashri V.T	Member
Mr. Navneet	External Member (Industry)

Members Absent:

Mr. Arun Salian	External Member (Industry)
Mr. Dharmendra Mehta	External Member (Industry)
Mr. Sanjay Singh	External Member (Industry)

At the outset, Keerthan Raj, Chairperson of the BOS in Commerce & Management, welcomed all the members present, explained the purpose of the meeting as mentioned in the notice and the agenda in brief. Then the agenda was taken up for discussion.

AGENDA 1: Continuation of Programs for the academic year 2022-23

Discussion: The continuation of existing programs with syllabus improvements wherever required were taken up for discussion to make the subjects more relevant and current in content. Innovative teaching pedagogy with experiential learning, projects, SWAYAM based learning was also suggested. The following programs had syllabus modifications –

1. Communicative English
2. Event Management
3. Cost Accounting - III Semester & IV Semester – Modifications in all units as per requirements.

RESOLUTION: The Board approved the continuation of programs and program changes were approved in principle and sought further approval from the academic council,

Proposed By: Prof. Amith Menezes

Seconded By: Prof. Keerthan Raj

At the end, the Chairperson thanked all the members for having spared their valuable time and extended their cooperation.

Keerthan Raj
14.07.22

Keerthan Raj
DEAN

Institute of Management and Commerce
Sri. Ivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

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PLACE: Mangaluru

Date: 14.07.22

PROCEEDINGS OF THE MEETING OF THE BOARD OF STUDIES OF THE COLLEGE OF MANAGEMENT & COMMERCE, SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY HELD On 04.01.2022 AT 3.30 P.M. IN THE CONFERENCE ROOM, 2ND FLOOR, PANDESHWARA CAMPUS, SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY.

Members Present:

Prof Keerthan Raj	Chairperson	
Prof. Amith Menezes	Member	
Prof. Nelson Periera	Member	
Dr. Shailashri V.T	Member	

Members Absent:

Mr. Navneet	External Member (Industry)
Mr. Arun Salian	External Member (Industry)
Mr. Dharmendra Mehta	External Member (Industry)
Mr. Sanjay Singh	External Member (Industry)

At the outset, Keerthan Raj, Chairperson of the BOS in Commerce & Management, welcomed all the members present, explained the purpose of the meeting as mentioned in the notice and the agenda in brief. Then the agenda was taken up for discussion.

AGENDA 1: Option of French & Sanskrit Language to be introduced in the UG NEP curriculum.

Discussion: Currently, Kannada, Malayalam and Hindi are being offered as languages in the NEP curriculum for first & second year UG students, as there is a demand from NRI students who have not studied any Indian language in high school, the members discussed the need to introduce French as an option and also bring in Sanskrit as an option under MIL. The codes would be denoted as YYProgramHN26K/M/H/F/S for respective languages.

RESOLUTION: The Board approved the inclusion of French and Sanskrit as language options in first and Second year.

Proposed By : Prof. Amith Menezes

Seconded By : Prof. Keerthan Raj

At the end, the Chairperson thanked all the members for having spared their valuable time and extended their cooperation.

Handwritten signature

Keerthan Raj

**DEAN
Chairperson**

Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

TRUE COPY

PLACE : Mangaluru

Date : 04.01.22

PROCEEDINGS OF THE MEETING OF THE BOARD OF STUDIES OF THE COLLEGE OF MANAGEMENT & COMMERCE, SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY HELD On 30.05.2022 AT 3.00 P.M. IN THE CONFERENCE ROOM, 2ND FLOOR, PANDESHWARA CAMPUS, SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY.

Members Present:

Prof Keerthan Raj	Chairperson	
Prof. Amith Menezes	Member	
Dr. Sonia Noronha	Member	
Prof. Nelson Periera	Member	
Dr. Shailashri V. T	Member	
Mr. Arun Salian	External Member (Industry)	
Mr. Sanjay Singh	External Member (Industry)	

Members Absent:

Mr. Dharmendra Mehta	External Member (Industry)
Mr. Navneet	External Member (Industry)

At the outset, Keerthan Raj, Chairperson of the BOS in Commerce & Management, welcomed all the members present, explained the purpose of the meeting as mentioned in the notice and the agenda in brief. Then the agenda was taken up for discussion.

AGENDA 1: Continuation of existing programs and academic calendar for the academic year.

Discussion : The board met to resolve the academic calendar and continuance of existing programs.

RESOLUTION : The Board approved the academic calendar for the new academic year to be sent for approval to the academic council.

AGENDA 2: The second year's course discussions and deliberations.

Discussion : The members discussed in detail on second year syllabus of various courses and certain changes were suggested. The members incorporated the suggestions in the syllabus and drafted updated syllabus.

RESOLUTION : The board drafted updated syllabus as approved by all the members.

Proposed By : Dr. Sonia Noronha

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Seconded By : Prof. Amith Menezes

At the end, the Chairperson thanked all the members for having spared their valuable time and extended their cooperation.

Keerthan Raj

DEAN
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

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PLACE : Mangaluru

Date : 30.5.22

REGISTRAR
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
MANGALORE

3

PROCEEDINGS OF THE MEETING OF THE BOARD OF STUDIES OF THE COLLEGE OF MANAGEMENT & COMMERCE, SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY HELD On 19.11.2021 AT 3.00 P.M. IN THE CONFERENCE ROOM, 2ND FLOOR, PANDESHWARA CAMPUS, SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY.

Members Present:

Prof Keerthan Raj	Chairperson	
Prof. Amith Menezes	Member	
Dr. Sonia Noronha	Member	
Mr. Dharmendra Mehta	External Member (Industry)	
Mr. Sanjay Singh	External Member (Industry)	
Prof. Nelson Pereira	Member	
Dr. Shailashri V.T	Member	

Members Absent:

Mr. Navneet	External Member (Industry)
Mr. Arun Salian	External Member (Industry)

At the outset, Keerthan Raj, Chairperson of the BOS in Commerce & Management, welcomed all the members present, explained the purpose of the meeting as mentioned in the notice and the agenda in brief. Then the agenda was taken up for discussion.

AGENDA 1: Option to pursue complete internship in final semester of BBA honours program.

Discussion : In line with the requirements in industry and to meet the demands of education with hands on learning in key domains, the board resolved to permit students to take up sixth semester internship to BBA Honours students as well.

RESOLUTION : The Board approved the option of internship in final semester to BBA Honours students as well.

Proposed By : Prof. Nelson Pereira

Seconded By : Dr. Sonia Noronha

At the end, the Chairperson thanked all the members for having spared their valuable time and cooperation.

Keerthan Raj
Chairperson
DEAN
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Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

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PLACE : Mangaluru

Date : 19.11.2021

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MANGALORE

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

SIXTH SEMESTER

INTERNSHIP AND PROJECT

VI Semester BBA Honours

Subject Code	Subject	Hours/Week	Credits	Marks
19BBAHN61	Internship /Entrepreneurship -Planning, Dissertation And Viva- Voce	20	20	700
		20	20	700

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PROCEEDINGS OF THE MEETING OF THE BOARD OF STUDIES OF THE COLLEGE OF MANAGEMENT & COMMERCE, SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY HELD On 16.07.2021 AT 3.30 P.M. IN THE CONFERENCE ROOM, 2ND FLOOR, PANDESHWARA CAMPUS, SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY.

Members Present:

Prof Keerthan Raj	Chairperson
Prof. Amith Menezes	Member
Dr. Sonia Noronha	Member
Mr. Dharmendra Mehta	External Member (Industry)
Mr. Sanjay Singh	External Member (Industry)
Mr. Daniel Perrera	External Member (Industry)

Members Absent:

Mr. Navneet	External Member (Industry)
Mr. Arun Salian	External Member (Industry)
Prof. Nelson Periera	Member
Dr. Shailashri V.T	Member

At the outset, Keerthan Raj, Chairperson of the BOS in Commerce & Management, welcomed all the members present, explained the purpose of the meeting as mentioned in the notice and the agenda in brief. Then the agenda was taken up for discussion.

AGENDA 1: Continuation of existing programs and academic calendar for the academic year.

Discussion : The board met to resolve the academic calendar and continuance of existing programs.

RESOLUTION : The Board approved the academic calendar for the new academic year which was delayed due to covid pandemic.

AGENDA 2: NEP clarifications

Discussion : The members discussed on various aspects of implementation of NEP and deliberated to seek guidance and go with the suggestions of the academic council for the new syllabus structure to be adopted.

RESOLUTION : The board resolved to await guidelines from the academic council on NEP implementation.

Proposed By : Prof. Nelson Periera

Seconded By : Prof. Amith Menezes

At the end, the Chairperson thanked all the members for having spared their valuable time and extended their cooperation.

Keerthan Raj

Chairperson

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Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

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PLACE : Mangaluru

Date : 16.07.21

REGISTRAR
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PROCEEDINGS OF THE MEETING OF THE BOARD OF STUDIES OF THE COLLEGE OF MANAGEMENT & COMMERCE, SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY HELD On 22.09.2020 AT 3.30 P.M. IN THE CONFERENCE ROOM, 2ND FLOOR, PANDESHWARA CAMPUS, SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY.

Members Present:

Prof Keerthan Raj	Chairperson	
Prof. Amith Menezes	Member	
Dr. Sonia Noronha	Member	
Prof. Nelson Periera	Member	
Dr. Shailashri V.T	Member	
Mr. Dharmendra Mehta	External Member (Industry)	
Mr. Sanjay Singh	External Member (Industry)	
Mr. Daniel Perrera	External Member (Industry)	

Members Absent:

Mr. Navneet	External Member (Industry)
Mr. Arun Salian	External Member (Industry)

At the outset, Keerthan Raj, Chairperson of the BOS in Commerce & Management, welcomed all the members present, explained the purpose of the meeting as mentioned in the notice and the agenda in brief. Then the agenda was taken up for discussion.

AGENDA 1: Inclusion of Research and Publication Ethics along with review of literature from 2020 in the course work for Management and Commerce.

Discussion: In adherence to UGC guidelines on ethics in research and establishment of CARE (Consortium for Research Ethics) it was proposed to include Research and Publication Ethics along with review of literature from 2020 in the course work for Management and Commerce

RESOLUTION: The board resolved to include Research and Publication Ethics along with review of literature from 2020 in the course work for Management and Commerce.

AGENDA 2: Introduction of Ph.D in Economics course work syllabus.

Discussion : The board members discussed and deliberated the syllabus for course work for Ph.D in economics for approval.

RESOLUTION: The board accepted the course work syllabus for Ph. D in Economics.

PROPOSED BY : Dr. Shailashree V.T.

SECONDED BY : Prof. Amith Menezes

At the end, the Chairperson thanked all the members for having spared their valuable time and extended their cooperation.

Keerthan Raj

Chairperson DEAN
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001
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PLACE : Mangaluru

Date : 22.09.20

REGISTRAR
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
MANGALORE

PROCEEDINGS OF THE MEETING OF THE BOARD OF STUDIES OF THE COLLEGE OF MANAGEMENT & COMMERCE, SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY HELD On 21.06.2020 AT 3.30 P.M. IN THE CONFERENCE ROOM, 2ND FLOOR, PANDESHWARA CAMPUS, SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY.

Members Present:

Prof Keerthan Raj	Chairperson
Prof. Amith Menezes	Member
Dr. Sonia Noronha	Member
Prof. Nelson Periera	Member
Dr. Shailashri V.T	Member
Mr. Dharmendra Mehta	External Member (Industry)
Mr. Sanjay Singh	External Member (Industry)
Mr. Daniel Perrera	External Member (Industry)

Members Absent:

Mr. Navneet	External Member (Industry)
Mr. Arun Salian	External Member (Industry)

At the outset, Keerthan Raj, Chairperson of the BOS in Commerce & Management, welcomed all the members present, explained the purpose of the meeting as mentioned in the notice and the agenda in brief. Then the agenda was taken up for discussion.

AGENDA 1: To revise the nomenclature of the Bachelor of Business Administration (BBA) program in Port Management to BBA in Port , Shipping Management & Logistics.

Discussion: With an increased thrust of the segment of logistics it was proposed to include the term Logistics in the nomenclature of the program BBA Port Management.

RESOLUTION: It is resolved that the nomenclature of the Bachelor of Business Administration (BBA) program in Port Management is changed to BBA in Port Logistics from this academic year onwards.

AGENDA 2: Academic Calendar finalisation for the year 2020 - 2021 as the batches got delayed due to covid situation to be discussed draft the calendar of events for the above said course.

RESOLUTION: The board approved the academic calendar to be sent for approval.

AGENDA 3: Appointment of BOE Chairperson for BBA, B.Com, M.Com and MBA courses for the academic year.

RESOLUTION: The board approved the chairperson and members of the board of examiners nominated by the chairperson for the year.

AGENDA 4: Syllabus changes and course modifications in various electives and course syllabus placed for discussion in alignment with the requirements of the industry and future in the electives offered programs of BBA (Logistics & Supply chain management), BBA (Port, Shipping Management & Logistics) for the year 2018-21 and 2019-22 and 2020-23 batches of students. As Logistics students did not have any papers on the super specialization topics in the syllabus of 2018-21, some subjects were to be included in the fifth semester, which was not included in the earlier BOS meeting.

DISCUSSION: As the syllabus needed more inclusiveness in offering super specialization knowledge and making the students industry ready, the member proposed changes in the syllabus as found appropriate for the benefit of the new batches as well as the current batches of students as under –

Syllabus Modifications:

Sl. No	Subject Code	Subject Name	Modification
1.	18BBALS56	Domestic & International Logistics	New subject introduced
2.	19BBALS45	Domestic & International Logistics	Syllabus Modifications
3.	20BBALS14	Principles of Logistics	New Subject Introduced
4.	20BBAPM45	Shipping Safety & Maintenance	New Subject Introduced
5.	20BBA15	Introduction to Port & Terminal Management	New Electives Introduced
6.	20BBA15	Hospital & Health System	Elective - Syllabus Modifications
7.	18BBALS55	Strategies In Procurement and Supply	New Electives Offered
8.	18BBALS57	Employability Skill Development V	New Electives Offered
9.	18BBAPM/LS58	Minor Project	New Electives Offered
10.	18BBALS54	Negotiation Skills in Contract & procurement	New Electives Offered
11.	18BBALS55	Strategies in Procurement & Supply	New Electives Offered
12.	18BBAPM54	International Trade Law	New Electives Offered
13.	18BBAPM55	Marine Financing & Insurance	New Electives Offered

RESOLUTION: Keeping a close connect with the industry and considering the changes in some of the sectors certain modifications are considered in the below mentioned subjects in terms of title change/modifications in the content /inclusion /deletion of certain concepts and hence the board resolved that the changes were necessary inline with the knowledge and updated information needed to be given to students as per requirements of the industry.

AGENDA 5: Proposal of new electives in undergraduate and post graduate levels in the college.

Discussion : The member proposed the starting of new programs in line with the demand for certain educational profiles in the industry - BBA Media Management, BBA integrated with USA CMA Syllabus, BBA IN Public Administration & Governance, BBA in Crisis Management, BBA in Rural Management, B.Com with Integrated USA- CMA, M.Com Financial Analytics, M.Com with USA-CMA, MBA with Hospital & Healthcare Management, MBA in Logistics & Supply Chain Management, MBA International Business, MBA in Banking & Financial Services, MBA in Retail Management, MBA in Public Administration & Governance, MBA in Rural Management.

RESOLUTION : The board approved the commencement of the new programs and moved the resolution to seek approval from the academic council.

PROPOSED BY : Keerthan Raj

SECONDED BY : Dr. Sonia N. & Prof. Amith Menezes

At the end, the Chairperson thanked all the members for having spared their valuable time and extended their cooperation.

Keerthan Raj

Chairperson

TRUE COPY

PLACE : Mangaluru

Date : 21.06.2020

REGISTRAR
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY,
MANGALORE

COLLEGE OF MANAGEMENT & COMMERCE

As per the powers conferred by the by-laws of the University the Vice Chancellor has nominated the dean, Prof. Keerthan Raj as the Chairperson of the Board of Studies of the College of Management & Commerce.

Vice Chancellor

I, Prof. Keerthan Raj, nominate the following members to the Board of Studies of the college for approval.

BOARD OF STUDIES 2020-23

Sl. No.	Name of the BOS Member	Designation
1	Prof. Keerthan Raj	Chairperson
2	Prof. Amith Menezes	Member
3	Dr. Sonia Noronha	Member
4	Dr. Shailashri V.T.	Member
5	Prof. Nelson Periera	Member
6	Mr. Sanjay Singh	External Member – Industry
7	Mr. Dharmendra B. Mehta B.G.L.,C.A., IRS (1990-2000 Batch)	External Member - Industry
8	Mr. Navneet	External Member- Industry
9	Mr. Arun Salian	External Member - Industry
10	Mr. Daniel Perrera	External Member - Industry

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PROCEEDINGS OF THE MEETING OF THE BOARD OF STUDIES OF THE COLLEGE OF MANAGEMENT & COMMERCE, SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY HELD ON 18.05.2020 AT 10.00 A.M. IN THE CONFERENCE ROOM, 2ND FLOOR, PANDESHWARA CAMPUS, SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY.

Members Present:

Prof Shailashri V T
Prof. Sonia Ajay
Prof Amith Menezes
Prof. Nelson Pereira
Mr. Sanjay Singh
Mr. Arun Salian
Mr Daniel Perrier

Chairperson
Member
Member
Member
Member (Industry)
Member (Industry)
Member (Industry)

Members Absent:

Mr. Dharmendra Mehta
Mr. Navneet

Member (Industry)
Member (Industry)

At the outset, Shailashri VT Chairperson of the BOS in Commerce & Management, welcomed all the members present, explained the purpose of the meeting as mentioned in the notice and the agenda in brief. Then the agenda was taken up for discussion.

AGENDA 1: Academic calendar for all UG & PG Courses and continuation of programs in the College of Management & Commerce and delayed calendar in view of Covid Pandemic lockdown for the year 2020-21

Discussion : The board approved the decision for the chairperson to take a decision based on academic council advise as the lockdown situation was unpredictable and an appropriate measures to be taken up with regard to decisions of syllabus completion, examinations and assessments as directed by the academic body from time to time.

RESOLUTION: Academic calendar for all UG & PG Courses and continuation of programs in the College of Management & Commerce was discussed, drafted and approved to be sent to the Registrar for due approval in view of Covid Pandemic lockdown. The board instructed the chairperson to take further decisions on the advice of the academic council, if uncertainty persisted.

AGENDA 2: Modifications and revisions in course syllabus, content and addition of new courses/electives.

Discussion: Various elective options were discussed at length and modifications in syllabus of certain courses were recommended. The board drafted the academic calendar for the academic year 2019-20 for approval.

RESOLUTION: Basis, lengthy discussion the board resolved certain modifications in content of the course and introduction of some new courses and/or electives and discontinuance of certain courses/electives and resolved to place the same in before the academic council. The board approved the academic calendar to be moved forward for approval.

Sl. No	Subject Code	Subject Name	Modification
1.	20BBA14	Fundamentals of Management	Content revision in Unit II
2.	20BBA15E	Organizational Behavior	Content revision in Unit IV
3.	20BBA15E	Introduction to Port & Terminal Management	New Subject Introduced
4.	20BBA24	Marketing Management	Content Revision
5.	20BBA26	Managerial Mathematics and Statistics	Content Revision
6.	20BBA18	Employability Skill Enhancement Program I	Subject changes with enhanced content
7.	20BBA28	Employability Skill Enhancement Program II	Subject changes with enhanced content
8.	20BBA38	Employability Skill Enhancement Program III	Subject changes with enhanced content
9.	20BBA48	Employability Skill Enhancement Program IV	Subject changes with enhanced content
10.	20BBA58	Employability Skill Enhancement Program V	Subject changes with enhanced content
11.	20BBA33E	Hospital Environment and Eco Policy	Course Unit Content changes
12.	20BBA34E	Hospital Operation Management	Course Unit Content changes
13.	20BBA45E	Hospital Health and Insurance Policy System	Course Unit Content changes
14.	20BBA54E	Hospital Support and Utility Services & Legal aspects	Title Modification and course unit content changes
15.	20BBA55E	Hospital Hazards and Disaster Management	Course Unit Content changes

Total Number of Papers in BBA: 44

Total modifications done: 15

Percentage of Modifications: 34%

B.Com :

Sl. No	Subject Code	Subject Name	Modification
1.	20BCMHN14-E2	Financial statement analysis and risk management	New Course Introduced (Elective)
2.	20BCMHN23-E2	Decision analysis and investment decision	New Course Introduced (Elective)
3.	20BCMHN28	Employability Skill Enhancement Program II	Subject changes with enhanced content
4.	20BCMHN32-E2	Cost Management And Internal Control	New Course Introduced (Elective)
5.	20BCMHN36-E2	Corporate Finance and Professional Ethics	New Course Introduced (Elective)
6.	20BCMHN38	Employability Skill Enhancement Program III	Subject changes with enhanced content
7.	20BCMHN43-E2	External Financial Reporting Decision/ Performance Management	Content Revision
8.	20BCMHN48	Employability Skill Enhancement Program IV	Subject changes with enhanced content
9.	20BCMHN51-E2	Planning Budgeting Forecasting Technology and Analytical	Subject changes with enhanced content
10.	20BCMHN58	Employability Skill Enhancement Program V	Subject changes with enhanced content
11.	20BCMHN68	Employability Skill Enhancement Program VI	Subject changes with enhanced content

Total Number of Papers in B.Com 44

Total modifications done 11

Percentage of Modifications: 25%

MBA & M.COM :

Sl. No	Subject Code	Subject Name	Modification
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1.	20MBA13	Economic Analysis for Business Decisions	Modification in Modules
2.	20MBA14	Leadership & Organizational Behavior	Modifications in Modules & Change of course title
3.	20MBA16	Legal Systems in Business	Modifications in Modules & Change of course title
4.	20MCOM13	Business Economics	Modification in Modules
5.	20MCOM14	Leadership & Organizational Behavior	Modifications in Modules & Change of course title
6.	20MBA16	Legal Systems in Business	Modifications in Modules & Change of course title
7.	20MBA22	Technology & Operations Management	Modifications in Modules & Change of course title
8.	20MBA23	Financial Management	Module Modifications
9.	20MBA24	Decision Science	Title Change
10.	20MBA25	Human Resource Management and Audit	Modifications in Modules & Change of course title
11.	20MBA26	Business Research Methods	Modifications in Modules & Change of course title
12.	20MBA27	Project on Indian Company Analysis & Publication – EAEP 2	New Course Introduced
13.	20MBA28	Managerial Personality Development - ESEP 2	New Course Introduced

Total Number of Papers in MBA: 25

Total modifications are done : 13

Percentage of Modifications: 52%

PROPOSED BY : Prof. Nelson Periera

SECONDED BY : Prof. Amith Menezes

At the end, the Chairperson thanked all the members for having spared their valuable time and extended their cooperation. The absent members were briefed on the minutes of the meeting.

Dr. Shailashri V. T.

Chairperson

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PLACE : Mangaluru

Date : 18.05.2020

DEAN
Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

REGISTRAR
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
MANGALORE

12

PROCEEDINGS OF THE MEETING OF THE BOARD OF STUDIES OF THE COLLEGE OF MANAGEMENT & COMMERCE, SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY HELD ON 21.09.2019 AT 3.30 P.M. IN THE CONFERENCE ROOM, 2ND FLOOR, PANDESHWARA CAMPUS, SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY.

Members Present:

Prof Shailashri V T	Chairperson	
Prof Amith Menezes	Member	
Prof. Nelson Pereira	Member	
Mr. Sanjay Singh	Member (-Industry)	
Mr. Arun Salian	Member (Industry)	
Mr. Daniel Perrier	Member (Industry)	

Members Absent:

Mr. Navneet	Member (Industry)	
Mr. Dharmendra Mehta	Member (Industry)	
Prof. Sonia Ajay	Member	

At the outset, Shailashri VT Chairperson of the BOS in Commerce & Management, welcomed all the members present, explained the purpose of the meeting as mentioned in the notice and the agenda in brief. Then the agenda was taken up for discussion.

AGENDA 1 : 1. Inclusion of Skill Development program in Undergraduate and postgraduate courses in association Xlanz Pvt. Ltd.,

Discussion: With a view to enhance the employability skills of the students the board moved the resolution to include Employability Skill Enhancement Program /Employability Skill Development 1, 2, 3.. as a course with two credits in every semester in the syllabus of all undergraduate and postgraduate programs. Currently a firm Xlanz had come forward to provide the course. Hence it was moved for approval to include Skill Development program in Undergraduate and postgraduate courses.

RESOLUTION: The board unanimously decided to adopt this new course for the benefit of all students with the aim of providing holistic education covering knowledge and skills for the future, The board advised the chairperson to continuously monitor the external agency and see to it that the requirements as per university guidelines are adhered. Also to train our own staff to run employability skill development programs in future.

AGENDA 2: Introduction of New Program and approval of syllabus for the new elective in undergraduate level in the college - BBA (Hospital Administration).

Discussion: The new super specialization elective of BBA - Hospital Administration was proposed by the board for approval by the academic council.

RESOLUTION: The board resolved as under –

Introduction of New Electives in Super Specialization Option as – BBA Hospital Administration and approval of the syllabus for the new programs in undergraduate level in the college.

AGENDA 3: : Changes in syllabus for BBA (CBCS) - Aviation Management, BBA (Port Management), B.Com and MBA.

DISCUSSION : Keeping a close connect with the industry and considering the changes in some of the sectors certain modifications are considered in the below mentioned subjects in terms of title change/modifications in the content /inclusion /deletion of certain concepts as under –

Course	Subject Code	Subject Name
BBA Aviation Management	19BBAAM33	Airline Marketing Management
	19BBAAM44	Airline Operations & Scheduling
	19BBAAM45	Air traffic Control and Management
	19BBAAM53	Cabin Crew Management
	19BBAAM55	Airline Finance

RESOLUTION: In order to improvise the learning and give better industry knowledge, certain subjects that needed improvisation in syllabus of BBA Aviation Management, changes to be incorporated have been discussed and the board approved the changes in the subjects of the programmes mentioned above.

AGENDA 4: Paper codes of first semester subjects uniformity for BBA & B.Com (all programs) to be made continuous and certain Syllabus changes in chapters 3,4,5 of the subject 17BCMHNICA154 Cost Accounting IV of final year B.Com and removal of the subject of 17BCMAM51 International Business for BBA Aviation Management students and having a common paper I7BCMHN/CAIAMS1 Business Ethics and Governance for all fifth semester B.Com students.

RESOLUTION: To bring in uniformity in the course paper codes and make it more meaningful as well as to avoid repetition in syllabus and certain chapters mentioned above was changed and it was resolved to have a common paper of Business Ethics and Governance for all B.Com students as it is relevant today.

PROPOSED BY : Prof. Amith Menezes

SECONDED BY : Prof. Nelson Periera

At the end, the Chairperson thanked all the members for having spared their valuable time and extended their cooperation.

Shailashri V. T.
Chairperson

BEAN
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

TRUE COPY

PLACE : Mangaluru

Date : 21.09.19

REGISTRAR
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
MANGALORE

PROCEEDINGS OF THE MEETING OF THE BOARD OF STUDIES OF THE COLLEGE OF MANAGEMENT & COMMERCE, SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY HELD ON 11.05.2019 AT 3.30 P.M. IN THE CONFERENCE ROOM, 2ND FLOOR, PANDESHWARA CAMPUS, SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY.

Members Present:

Prof Shailashri V T	Chairperson
Prof. Sonia Ajay	Member
Prof Amith Menezes	Member
Prof. Nelson Pereira	Member
Mr. Sanjay Singh	Member (Industry)
Mr. Arun Salian	Member (Industry)

Members Absent:

Mr. Dharmendra Mehta	Member (Industry)
Mr. Navneet	Member (Industry)
Mr Daniel Perrier	Member (Industry)

At the outset, Shailashri VT Chairperson of the BOS in Commerce & Management, welcomed all the members present, explained the purpose of the meeting as mentioned in the notice and the agenda in brief. Then the agenda was taken up for discussion.

AGENDA 1: Academic Calendar for the year 2019 – 2020 and continuation of programs and introduction of new electives and discontinuance of certain electives at UG and PG levels.

Discussion: Various elective options were discussed at length and modifications in syllabus of certain courses were recommended. The board drafted the academic calendar for the academic year 2019-20 for approval.

RESOLUTION: Basis, lengthy discussion the board resolved certain modifications in content of the course and introduction of some new courses, namely, value added courses with a minimum of 30 contact hours and/or electives and discontinuance of certain courses/electives and resolved to place the same in before the academic council. The board approved the academic calendar to be moved forward for approval.

BBA :

Sl. No	Subject Code	Subject Name	Modification
1.	19BBA54E	Negotiation Skills in Contract & Procurement	Revision in Course Title, content modifications of Unit III, IV , V contents and semester of offering
2.	19BBA55E	Strategies in Procurement & Supply	Revision in Course Title, content modifications of Unit IV , V contents and semester of offering

3.	19BBA56E	Domestic & International Logistics	Revision in unit II, III of course and semester of offering
4.	19BBA58	Minor Project in Port, Shipping Management or Logistics Company	New Subject/Course Introduced (Elective)
5.	19BBA18	Employability Skill Enhancement Program	New Subject Introduced
6.	19BBA28	Employability Skill Enhancement Program	New Subject Introduced
7.	19BBA38	Employability Skill Enhancement Program	New Subject Introduced
8.	19BBA48	Employability Skill Enhancement Program	New Subject Introduced
9.	19BBA58	Employability Skill Enhancement Program	New Subject Introduced
10.	19BBA45	Shipping Safety & Maintenance	New Subject Introduced

Total Number of Papers in BBA: 44

Total modifications done: 10

Percentage of Modifications: 23%

B.COM:

Sl. No	Subject Code	Subject Name	Modification
1.	19BCMHN24	Marketing Management	Module modifications of Unit V
2.	19BCMHN43	E-commerce	New Course Introduced in place of GST and Stock Market
3.	19BCMHN54	Cost Accounting IV	All the Module modified
4.	19BCMHN65	Business Taxation	New Module introduced In place of Unit III and V
5.	19BCMHN18	Employability Skill Enhancement Program I	New Subject Introduced
6.	19BCMHN28	Employability Skill Enhancement Program II	New Subject Introduced
7.	19BCMHN38	Employability Skill Enhancement Program III	New Subject Introduced
8.	19BCMHN48	Employability Skill Enhancement Program IV	New Subject Introduced
9.	19BCMHN58	Employability Skill Enhancement Program V	New Subject Introduced

10.	19BCMHN68	Employability Skill Enhancement Program VI	New Subject Introduced
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Total Number of Papers in B.Com : 44

Total modifications done: 10

Percentage of Modifications: 23%

MBA & M.Com :

Total Number of Papers in MBA : 25

Total modifications are done : 15

Percentage of Modifications: 60%

Sl. No	Subject Code	Subject Name	Modification
1.	19MBA13	Principles of Management	Modification in Modules
2.	19MCOM13	Contemporary Management Concepts & Thoughts	Modifications in Modules
3.	19MBA14	Organizational Behavior & Managerial Communication	New Modules Introduced
4.	19MCOM14	Organizational Theory & Behavior	Modifications in Modules
5.	19MBA16	Industry Analysis	New Course Introduced
6.	19MBA22	Production & Operations Management	Module Modifications of Unit IV
7.	19MBA26	Business Research Methods	Module Modifications
8.	19MBA27	Indian Company Analysis	New Course Introduced
9.	19MBADEM36	Dual Elective Marketing	Module Modifications
10.	19MBAEH34	Industrial & Employee Relations	Module Modifications
11.	19MBADEH36	Dual Elective HRM	Module Modifications

12.	19MBA18	Employability Skill Development Program – ESEP I	New Course Introduced
13.	19MBA28	Employability Skill Development Program – ESEP II	New Course Introduced
14.	19MBA38	Employability Skill Development Program – ESEP III	New Course Introduced
15.	19MBA48	Employability Skill Development Program – ESEP IV	New Course Introduced

AGENDA 2: Appointment of panel of examiners, chairperson and evaluators for the academic year.

RESOLUTION: The board approved the panel of examiners, chairperson proposed by the chairperson.

PROPOSED BY : Prof. Nelson Pereira

SECONDED BY : Prof. Sonia Ajay

At the end, the Chairperson thanked all the members for having spared their valuable time and extended their cooperation. The absent members were briefed on the minutes of the meeting.

Prof. Shailashri V. T.

Chairperson

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PLACE : Mangaluru

Date : 11.05.19

REGISTRAR
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
MANGALORE

PROCEEDINGS OF THE MEETING OF THE BOARD OF STUDIES OF THE COLLEGE OF MANAGEMENT & COMMERCE, SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY HELD ON 05.03.2018 AT 3.00 P.M. IN THE CONFERENCE ROOM, 2ND FLOOR, PANDESHWARA CAMPUS, SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY.

Members Present:

Prof Shailashri V T	Chairperson
Prof. Sonia Ajay	Member
Prof Amith Menezes	Member
Prof. Nelson Pereira	Member
Mr. Sanjay Singh	Member (Industry)

Members Absent:

Mr. Dharmendra Mehta	Member (Industry)
Mr. Navneet	Member (Industry)
Mr Daniel Perrier	Member (Industry)
Mr. Arun Salian	Member (Industry)

At the outset, Shailashri VT Chairperson of the BOS in Business management and commerce, welcomed all the members present, explained the purpose of the meeting as mentioned in the notice and the agenda in brief. Then the agenda was taken up for discussion.

AGENDA 1: Nomenclature changes of an undergraduate & Postgraduate course in BBA & MBAIG -

1. Paper title of “ Workshop on Ethics & Culture”, Indian Company Analysis & Corporate Social Responsibility (17MBAIG19) TO Workshop on Indian Company Analysis & Corporate Social Responsibility

2. Paper titled “ Visit to Domestic Airport & Indian Airline Company Analysis, Ethics & Culture & Corporate Social Responsibility (17BBAAM19) TO “ Visit to Domestic Airport, Indian Airline Company Analysis & Corporate Social Responsibility” (17BBAAM19)

Discussion: The board discussed on the proposal of modification in the nomenclature of undergraduate courses of 17MBAIG19 and 17BBAAM19.

RESOLUTION: In need of the hour to have practical exposure to students, the board has approved the syllabus Updation of undergraduate and post graduate course to introduce corporate ethics and company analysis in one course so as to have a totality of undertsanding of the concept of Corprate Ethics in the real world.

1. Paper title of “ Workshop on Ethics & Culture”, Indian Company Analysis & Corporate Social Responsibility (17MBAIG19) TO Workshop on Indian Company Analysis & Corporate Social Responsibility

2. Paper titled “ Visit to Domestic Airport & Indian Airline Company Analysis, Ethics & Culture & Corporate Social Responsibility (17BBAAM19) TO “ Visit to Doemstic Airport, Indian Airline Company Analysis & Corporate Social Responsibility” (17BBAAM19).

Agenda 2: Introduction of New Program and approval of syllabus for the new programs in undergraduate and post graduate level in the college.

Discussion : With a requirement to have more super specialization programs catering to wider requirements and the growing vistas in business domains requiring expertise in specific fields, new programs were tabled for discussion and approval. A discussion on the syllabus to be incorporated was taken up and approved to the recommended to the board in undergraduate and post graduate level in the college. The programs are –

1. M.COM
2. MBA (Evening Program) for working professionals
3. BBA Port Management
4. BBA (International Business) in assn with I nurture, Bangalore
5. BBA (Financial Services) in assn with I nurture, Bangalore
6. MBA Port Management

RESOLUTION: The board approved the introduction and moved the resolution to seek approval from the academic council the programs of M.COM, MBA (Evening program for working professionals), BBA Port Management, MBA Port Management and a collaboration program of BBA (International Business) & BBA (Financial Services) in assn with I nurture, Bangalore

Agenda 3: Syllabus of the new programs

Discussion: The board discussed the syllabus to be incorporated for the new programs and the structure of running the collaborated program. The academic calender for the MBA (Evening program was drafted and moved for approval.

Resolution: The board approved the syllabus and instructed the chairperson to coordinate with the collaborators to guide them on the pattern, scheme and structure of the undergraduate program in Srinivas University so as to be in alignment with our academic and evaluation requirements and further advised the chairperson to closely monitor the program and hand hold the running of the program and update the board.

PROPOSED BY : Prof. Amith Menezes

SECONDED BY : Prof. Sonia Ajay

At the end, the Chairperson thanked all the members for having spared their valuable time and extended their cooperation.

Shailashri V. T.

DEAN
Chairperson
Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

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PLACE : Mangaluru

Date : 05.03.18

REGISTRAR
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
MANGALORE

18

PROCEEDINGS OF THE MEETING OF THE BOARD OF STUDIES OF THE COLLEGE OF MANAGEMENT & COMMERCE, SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY HELD ON 16.01.2018 AT 3.30 P.M. IN THE CONFERENCE ROOM, 2ND FLOOR, PANDESHWARA CAMPUS, SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY.

Members Present:

Prof Shailashri V T	Chairperson
Prof. Sonia Ajay	Member
Prof Amith Menezes	Member
Prof. Nelson Pereira	Member
Dr. Ramesh Pai	Member
Mr. Sanjay Singh	Member (Industry)
Mr. Navneet	Member (Industry)

Members Absent:

Mr. Dharmendra Mehta	Member (Industry)
Mr Daniel Perrier	Member (Industry)
Mr. Arun Salian	Member (Industry)

At the outset, Shailashri VT Chairperson of the BOS in Business management and commerce, welcomed all the members present, explained the purpose of the meeting as mentioned in the notice and the agenda in brief. Then the agenda was taken up for discussion.

Agenda-I: Continuation of Graduate and Post-graduate programs in and updation of syllabus changes needed for the academic year 2018-19 onwards.

Discussion: The board discussed on the in line with the industry requirements to have students who have a blend of industry exposure and to increase their exposure to the practical workings of the theoretical concepts and develop research abilities in students. It was decided to -

1. Introduce Industry and company analysis course with 2 credits in all programs in specific semesters
2. Industrial training/internship in specific semester
3. Increase in experimental learning and reducing classroom teaching in the teaching pedagogy in the curriculum.
4. Focus on minor projects to give choices of electives and increase value addition to theoretical study.

Resolution: The board discussed at length and approved the proposal as under –

1. Introduce Industry and company analysis course with 2 credits in all programs in specific semesters
2. Industrial training/internship in specific semester
3. Increase in experimental learning and reducing classroom teaching in the teaching pedagogy in the curriculum.
4. Introduce minor projects of 2 credits to give choices of electives and increase value addition to theoretical study.

With this agenda to be actioned the board of studies members discussed at length and agreed to implement the following changes in the courses of BBA, B.Com and MBA programs unanimously.

Sl. No	Subject Code	Subject Name	Modification
1.	18BBA18	Workshop on Indian Company Analysis and Corporate Social Responsibility	New subject introduced
2.	18BBA28E28	Shipping Company Analysis & Corporate Social Responsibility	New Elective introduced
3.	18BBA23E	Marine Resource Management	New Elective Introduced
4.	18BBA34E	Marine EXIM Documentation and Procedure	New Elective Introduced
5.	18BBA37E	Marine Industry Outlook	New Elective Introduced
6.	18BBA38E	Visit to Port Cargo Division and Report	New Subject Introduced (Elective)
7.	18BBA44E	Marine Traffic Management	New Subject Introduced (Elective)
8.	18BBA46E1	Retail Management	New Subject Introduced (Elective)
9.	18BBA46E2	Procurement and Supply Management	New Subject Introduced (Elective)
10.	18BBA54E	International trade law	New Subject Introduced (Elective)
11.	18BBA58E	Domestic & International Logistics	New Subject Introduced (Elective)
12.	18BBA62E	Negotiation Skills in Procurement and supply	New Subject Introduced (Elective)
13.	18BBA63E	Relationship management in procurement and supply	New Subject Introduced (Elective)
14.	18BBA64	Industry Internship	Practical Exposure Course introduced

Total modifications are done: 14

Percentage of Modifications: 32%

B.Com :

Sl. No	Subject Code	Subject Name	Modification
1.	18BCMHN11	Business Communication I	New Modules Introduced
2.	18BCMHN21	Business Communication II	New Modules Introduced
3.	18BCMHN33	Auditing And Assurance	Module Modifications Of Unit V
4.	18BCMHN34	Business Law	Module Modifications Of Unit IV
5.	18BCMHN36	Banking And Insurance	Module Modifications Of Unit IV
6.	18BCMHN47	Business Research Methods	New Modules Introduced
7.	18BCMHN48	Life Skills Development	New Modules Introduced
8.	18BCMHN43	E- Commerce	Module Modifications Of Unit V
9.	18BCMHN51	Business Ethics And Governance	Module Modifications Of Unit V
10.	18BCMHN53	Strategic Management	Module Modifications Of Unit II
11.	17BCMHN61	International Business	Module Modifications Of Unit I

Total Number of Papers in B.Com: 44

Total modifications are done: 11

Percentage of Modifications : 25%

MBA :

Sl. No	Subject Code	Subject Name	Modification
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1. Introduce Industry and company analysis course with 2 credits in all programs in specific semesters
2. Industrial training/internship in a specific semester
3. Increase in experimental learning, value-added courses and reduce classroom teaching in the teaching pedagogy in the curriculum.
4. Introduce minor projects of 2 credits to give choices of electives and increase value addition to theoretical study.

With this agenda to be actioned the board of studies members discussed at length and agreed to implement the following changes in the courses of BBA, B.Com and MBA programs unanimously.

Sl. No	Subject Code	Subject Name	Modification
1.	18BBA18	Workshop on Indian Company Analysis and Corporate Social Responsibility	New subject introduced
2.	18BBA28E28	Shipping Company Analysis & Corporate Social Responsibility	New Elective introduced
3.	18BBA23E	Marine Resource Management	New Elective introduced
4.	18BBA34E	Marine EXIM Documentation and Procedure	New Elective Introduced
5.	18BBA37E	Marine Industry Outlook	New Elective Introduced
6.	18BBA38E	Visit to Port Cargo Division and Report	New Subject Introduced (Elective)
7.	18BBA44E	Marine Traffic Management	New Subject Introduced (Elective)
8.	18BBA46E1	Retail Management	New Subject Introduced (Elective)
9.	18BBA46E2	Procurement and Supply Management	New Subject Introduced (Elective)
10.	18BBA54E	International trade law	New Subject Introduced (Elective)
11.	18BBA58E	Domestic & International Logistics	New Subject Introduced (Elective)
12.	18BBA62E	Negotiation Skills in Procurement and supply	New Subject Introduced (Elective)
13.	18BBA63E	Relationship management in procurement and supply	New Subject Introduced (Elective)
14.	18BBA64	Industry Internship	Practical Exposure Course introduced

Total Number of Papers in BBA: 44

1.	18MBA11	Economic Analysis for Business Decisions	New Modules Introduced
2.	18MBA12	Business Statistics and Analytics	New Modules Introduced
3.	18MBA14	Organizational Behavior & Managerial Communication	Module Modifications of Unit V & VI
4.	18MBA16	Business Law	Module Modifications of Unit V
5.	18MBA21	Marketing Management	Module Modifications of Unit IV
6.	18MBA25	Human Resource Management	New Modules Introduced
7.	18MBAEM35	Consumer Behaviour & Marketing Research	New Modules Introduced

Total Number of Papers in MBA :25

Total modifications are done: 7

Percentage of Modifications : 28%

Agenda 2 – Preparation of academic calendar and panel of examiner and evaluators for the academic year.

Discussion: The academic calendar was drafted and presented to the board and the panel of examiners and evaluators for all UG & PG courses was prepared.

Resolution: The Board discussed and resolved to accept the academic calendar and panel of examiners and evaluators and recommended to be sent for approval.

Proposed by : Prof. Nelson Periera

Seconded By : Prof. Amith Menezes

PROCEEDINGS OF THE MEETING OF THE BOARD OF STUDIES OF THE COLLEGE OF MANAGEMENT & COMMERCE, SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY HELD ON 31.03.2017 AT 3.00 P.M. IN THE CONFERENCE ROOM, 2ND FLOOR, PANDESHWARA CAMPUS, SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY.

Members Present:

Prof Shailashri V T
Prof. Sonia Ajay
Prof Amith Menezes
Prof. Nelson Perirera
Dr. Ramesh Pai
Mr. Sanjay Singh
Mr. Dharmendra Mehta
Mr. Navneet

Chairperson
Member
Member
Member
Member
Member (Industry)
Member (Industry)
Member (Industry)

Members Absent:

Mr Daniel Perrier Member (Industry)
Mr. Arun Salian Member (Industry)

At the outset, Mrs. Shailashri V.T. Chairperson of the BOS in Business Management and Commerce, welcomed all the members present, explained the purpose of the meeting as mentioned in the notice and the agenda in brief. Then the agenda was taken up for discussion.

Agenda-1: The decisions on the programs to be introduced in the college and finalising a list of programs to be offered in line with the need and opportunities in the business world to be introduced in the college – BBA (H), BBA(Aviation) ,BBA(logistics), MBA (IG), B.COM(H), B.COM(ACCA), B.Com(CA), B.com(Aviation), MBA.

Discussion: The Chairperson explained briefly about the establishment of Srinivas University and the programs being introduced under. She provided the draft syllabus of the undergraduate and PG programs in the faculty of Business management and commerce prepared by the Faculty of the college. She explained the commitment of the University and gave an overview of Srinivas University Regulations for the UG and PG programs and requested the Board to deliberate on the agenda and take appropriate decision and help the university to continue the above said programs from the academic year 2018 onwards. The BoS members discussed the agenda in detail and

drafted the course curriculum including the scheme of instruction, eligibility criteria, etc. for the undergraduate and post graduate programs in Business management and commerce.

Resolution: The Board discussed at length, gave suggestions and unanimously resolved to recommend to the University to adopt the new PG and UG programs as proposed - to be offered in line with the need and opportunities in the business world to be introduced in the college – BBA (H), BBA(Aviation), BBA(logistics), MBA (IG), B.COM(H), B.COM(ACCA), B.Com(CA), B.com(Aviation), MBA.

Agenda 2:The Regulations of BBA Courses were formed and discussed in great detail.

Resolution: The Board resolved to recommend to the University to accept the regulations for the BBA Courses of College of Management and Commerce.

Agenda 3 :The Regulations of B.Com Courses were formed and discussed in great detail.

Resolution: The Board resolved to recommend to the University to accept the regulations for the B.Com Courses of College of Management and Commerce.

Agenda 4 :The Regulations of MBA Courses were formed and discussed in great detail.

Resolution: The Board resolved to recommend to the University to accept the regulations for the MBA Courses of College of Management and Commerce.

Agenda 5 : The syllabus and academic calendar finalization.

Discussion: The Board members had come prepared with syllabus content for discussion, the same was deliberated and resolved as under.

Resolution : The Board recommended certain content and finalised the academic calendar and syllabus for the programs for approval.

Agenda 6: The scheme of instruction, scheme of examination and Curriculum and preparation of academic Calendar. panel of evaluators formation for the academic year

Discussion : The Chairperson explained the guidelines relating to scheme of examination and pattern of question papers and requested the Board to work out the Scheme of Examination and decide about the pattern of question papers to be adopted for the said programs. Accordingly the Board went through the guidelines of the Scheme of Examination provided to the board and prepared the detailed scheme of examination and pattern of question papers for UG and PG courses in business management and commerce and resolved as under.

Resolution: The panel of evaluators was finalised and approved by the board.

AGENDA 6: Course work syllabus of Ph. D in the college of Management & Commerce in the fields of Management / Commerce.

Discussion : The Board discussed the modalities of accepting transferred admissions and drafted the course work syllabus for the Ph.D Program and the regulations of D.Litt., and Post doctoral program.

RESOLUTION: In a very lengthy deliberation the board approved the draft for approval to the academic council body on the above programs.

Proposed by:

Dr. Shailashri V.T.

Seconded By:

Prof. Amith Menezes & Prof. Sonia Ajay

At the end, the Chairperson thanked all the members for having spared their valuable time and extended their cooperation.

Shailashri V. T. DEAN

Chairperson

TRUE COPY

PLACE : Mangaluru

Date : 31.03.2017

Institute of Management and Commerce
Srinivas University
Mangaluru - 575 001

REGISTRAR
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
MANGALORE